

Effects of Interactive and Collaborative Learning Strategies on Academic Performance of Social Studies Students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of interactive and collaborative learning strategies on the academic performance of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State. This study employed a 2x2x2 quasi-experimental design. This study sample comprised 160 upper basic eight students from six sampled schools in both urban and rural areas. The research instrument used for this study was tagged “Social Studies Performance Test” (SSPT). Mean, standard deviation, t-test (t) and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) were used to analyse the data collected. The results showed that the treatment had an effect on the experimental groups. Students who were not exposed to treatment do not perform well. The results also showed an effect by sex; the mean scores of the experimental groups were better than those of the control group. Based on these findings, it was therefore concluded that the treatment had an effect on the experimental groups compared to the control group. As a result, it was thus recommended, among other things, that there is an urgent need for teachers to re-appraise the use of instructional learning strategies employed in the teaching and learning process in Social Studies in schools.

Keywords: Interactive, Collaborative, Learning Strategies, Academic Performance and Social Studies Student.

Introduction

It is believed that by using appropriate learning strategies to transmit the right type of knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes, the Nigerian Social Studies goals of instilling the spirit of nationalism and patriotism in the Nigerian learner will be realised. Each school subject is designed and structured to meet specific aspects of human needs; this is accomplished through the development of awareness, experience, and understanding, allowing humans to discover the being in themselves as individuals and people. This is because man, including the basic education learner, is a social being who forms social relationships with other human beings

through interaction and collaboration. To meet these human needs and desires, social relationships and social institutions are formed. Education, as a social institution, enables man to become socially human through community, association, integration, and participation in humanity's common inheritance.

The purpose of Social Studies as a subject is to instil and encourage the spirit of social integration, nationalism, and patriotism in Nigerian primary school students. This is because, like other independent African states in the twentieth century, Nigeria and its citizens were unaware that they belonged to a nation-state. Except for a few, African countries were created by European imperialism (Kalusi & Ireyefoju, 2019). With this in mind, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2004; 2014) emphasizes the importance of education in instilling national consciousness and unity, faith in man's ability to make rational decisions, moral and spiritual values in interpersonal and human relationships, shared responsibility for the common good of society, and respect for the dignity of labor, among other goals. It also acknowledges man as the ultimate measure of all things when it states that education will result in an independent-thinking being or learner. Unfortunately, this goal appears to be out of reach because, as effective as the philosophy and national education goals seem to be, they have yet to point to this indivisible nationhood.

Nigeria aimed to build, among other things, a strong and self-sufficient nation in which people identified themselves as Nigerians rather than as members of ethnic nationalities, and where they

could live freely in any part of the country to achieve national unity. The burden of carrying out this intention falls squarely on the shoulders of education, as the ultimate instrument.

The process by which learners learn together through face-to-face contact or interactive model tools, such as the computer, is known as the Interactive Learning Strategy (ILS). Active learning strategies include interactive learning strategies. They are part of an inquiry community exploring a theoretical framework that offers opportunities for a group of learners to engage in purposeful, critical discourse and reflection, with the goal of constructing personal meaning and mutual understanding, among other benefits. Building personal meaning and mutual understanding through learning strategies promotes the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes that aid the learner in their process of becoming human in their environment. These strategies are designed to help the learner develop specific skills that will equip them as effective problem solvers in a world full of uncertainties and contradictions. Such knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes enable the learner to see beyond ignorance or the "natural attitude." According to Ireyefoju (2014), the "natural attitude" is a pre-philosophic tradition in which people accept things as they are because they believe that things are truly what they appear to be. The natural attitude refers to the mindset people adopt in everyday life, where they tend to take things for granted.

The Interactive Learning Strategy (ILS) emphasises the dynamic nature of learners' interactions with their peers, teachers, and others with whom they interact. It is based on the premise that any learning that occurs in the classroom results from the interaction of the players. The interactive strategy is appealing from both the teacher's and the learner's perspectives because it is an active

approach to learning and teaching that breathes life, freedom, and creativity into what is often a tedious, ineffective, and constrained formal approach to teaching, with the teacher assuming the role of a leader, rule enforcer, and learner evaluator. Learners and teachers share responsibility for learning and teaching in this strategy (Eastman et al, 2011). The Interactive Learning Strategy also emphasises the learner's independent activity, the organisation of a self-learning environment, and experimental and practical training. This is due to the learner's freedom of action and use of initiative, as well as flexible training programs that allow the learner to work at their own pace (Yakovleva et al., 2015).

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in the mean scores of Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?
2. What is the effect on the mean scores of male and female Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

- i. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.
- ii. There is no significant effect between the mean scores of urban and rural Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test post-test control group design. It was a 2 x 2 x 2 factorial design. Interactive Learning Strategy (ILS) and Collaborative Learning Strategy (CLS) as treatment groups I and II. The population of this study consisted of all 15,355 Upper Basic eight students in Bomadi/Burutu/Patani Education Zone in Delta State. The study sample comprises one hundred and sixty (160) Upper Basic eight students from six sampled schools in urban and rural areas. The instrument for this study was the Social Studies Performance Test (SSPT). It consisted of fifty (50) multiple-choice items sampled from the Past Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) questions set by the Ministry of Basic Education of Delta State, Asaba. The reliability of the instrument was established using thirty (30) students from secondary schools outside the sampled area for the first and second administrations. The reliability coefficient was computed using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient, and a value of 0.83 was obtained. The value indicates that the instrument yielded scores that were stable over time, making them suitable for the present study. The experiment lasted for six (6) weeks. The data collected from the pre-test and post-test were subjected to statistical analysis using descriptive statistics, including the mean. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the various hypotheses.

Results

RQ1: What is the difference in the mean scores of Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean Scores of Students' Achievement based on Sex, Collaborative and Traditional Strategies

Instructional Strategies/Treatment	Pretest			Posttest			Mean Gain
	N	X	SD	N	X	SD	
Interactive Strategy (E1)	66	42.45	2.23	66	84.16	4.68	41.70
Collaborative Strategy (E2)	66	41.86	2.16	66	70.05	13.36	28.19
Total	132	42.16		132	77.11		34.95

Table 1 presents the mean achievement test scores of Social Studies students, based on the use of interactive and collaborative learning strategies. The pretest scores indicated that, prior to treatment, students using the interactive strategy had a mean score of 42.45. For the collaborative group, at pretest, the mean score was 41.86. However, the posttest results showed that students using the interactive strategy had a mean score of 84.16, while those using the collaborative strategy had a mean score of 70.05. The results further showed that there were marginal differences in performance in both interactive and collaborative strategies. To ascertain whether the observed differences were significant, hypothesis 3 was tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

RQ2: What is the effect on the mean scores of urban and rural Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean scores of urban and rural Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

Instructional Strategies/Treatment	Pre-Test				Post-Test			Mean Gain
	Location	N	X	SD	N	SD	X	
Collaborative Strategy (E1)	Urban	66	43.09	2.29	66	4.95	83.43	40.34
	Rural	54	41.95	2.24	54	14.03	69.95	28.00
Traditional Strategy (Control Group)	Urban	66	42.69	2.39	66	3.97	84.64	41.94
	Rural	54	42.39	2.14	54	13.14	70.73	28.33
Total		240	42.53		240		77.19	34.65

Table 2 showed that the mean, standard deviation of Social Studies students' achievement test scores based on collaborative strategy, traditional strategy and school location. The pre-test scores showed that before treatment urban students have mean of 43.09 and standard deviation of 2.29. The rural students have 41.95 with standard deviation of 2.24. For the control group, urban and rural students have mean scores of 42.69 and 42.39 with standard deviation of 2.39 and 2.14 respectively. However, the post-test showed that in the experimental group (collaborative strategy), urban students have mean score of 83.43 with a standard deviation of 4.95 and rural students have a mean score of 69.95 with standard deviation of 14.03. For the control group, while urban students have a mean score of 84.64 with a mean of 3.97, rural students have a mean of 70.73 with a standard deviation of 13.14. The results further showed that there were marginal differences in performance, except for the higher difference in the performance of urban and rural students in the experimental group. The treatments seem to favour both treatment and control groups. However, the overall results showed that there was effect of treatments on both experimental and control group. This was because the post-test mean scores were higher for both experimental and control groups hence the high performance in the achievement test. To ascertain whether the observed differences were significant, hypothesis 5 was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.

Table 3: T-Test Analysis of Learning Strategies and Students’ Performance

	Learning Strategies	t	df	Sig.(2 tailed)	Mean Diff.	Std. Error Diff.	95% Confidence Interval of the Diff.	
							Lower	Upper
Pre-Test	Interactive Strategy	-2.391	158	.018	-.81250	.3398	-1.4836	-.14143
	Collaborative Strategy	-2.391	153.34	.018	-.81250	.3398	-1.4836	-.1427
Post-Test	Interactive Strategy	-9.838	158	.000	-12.738	1.295	-15.2947	-10.1803
	Collaborative Strategy	-9.838	106.92	.000	-12.738	1.295	-15.2947	-10.1708

This analysis of t-test statistics showed pre-test and post-test scores for interactive learning strategy and collaborative learning strategy. Whereas pre-test and post-test mean scores and standard deviation for interactive learning strategy were 42.1000, 1.95260; 71.2375, 10.64888 respectively, the pre-test and post-test mean scores and standard deviation for collaborative learning strategy were 42.9125, 2.32865; 83.9750, 4.55063 respectively. The t-test scores for both pre-test and post-test were -2.391, -2.391 and -9.8385 and -9.8385 respectively at $p = .018$ and $.000$. Based on this analysis, this result further showed that there was significant difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students in the SSPT. The implication of this result was that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. And the alternate hypothesis which stated that “There is significant difference between the mean scores of Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State” was not rejected at the same significant level. It means that there was effect of treatment on Social Studies students’ academic performance. And it was concluded that there was significant difference between the mean

scores of Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant effect between the mean scores of urban and rural Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.

Table 4: Analysis of ANCOVA of Students’ Sex and Learning Strategies in SSPT

Source	Type III Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	29314.679 ^a	7	4187.811	64.876	.000
Intercept	371.012	1	371.012	5.748	.000
Location* Interactive Strategy* Collaborative Strategy* Pre-test	29314.679	7	4187.811	64.876	.000
Error	14975.721	232	64.551		
Total	1230392.000	240			
Corrected Total	44290.400	239			

The analysis of covariance showed that there was effect of treatment on the experimental group. The results further showed the F as 64.876 and mean square of 4187.811 supported this claim of significant difference in the mean scores at $P = .000$. The null hypothesis which stated there is no significant effect between the mean scores of urban and rural Social Studies students exposed to interactive and collaborative learning strategies in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State. was rejected. Thus, there is significant effect between the mean scores of urban and rural Social Studies students exposed to interactive learning strategy and collaborative learning strategy in Upper Basic Schools.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this research on the impact of instructional learning techniques on the academic performance of Upper Basic Learners in Social Studies revealed that the experimental groups' mean scores on the SSPT were higher than the control group's mean scores. This was a consequence of the therapeutic impact. The SSPT therapy specifically affected the sex of the Upper Basic Learner. The experimental group's mean scores were higher than those of the control group's, on average. The same applied to the site of the school. In the experimental groups, the mean score for Upper Basic learners was greater than the mean score for those exposed to the conventional learning technique. To examine the impact of the intervention on students' performance in Social Studies Education, two experimental groups and a control group were established. The treatment groups employed an interactive learning method and a collaborative learning strategy, whereas the control group used a standard learning strategy. In light of this, an intact class was employed while taking the following moderating factors into consideration: sex and school district. Using descriptive mean scores, standard deviation, t-test, and analysis of covariance inferential statistics, seven research questions and seven hypotheses were developed and assessed. The explanation of the study's results was centered on how the moderating factors, such as sex, school location, and instructional learning styles, affected the academic performance of Social Studies students.

The examined hypotheses regarding student academic achievement, instructional learning styles, and school location all supported this. However, there was no statistical significance in

the mean results for the interactive and conventional learning strategies. In other words, neither the experimental group nor the control group had any effects from the therapy. This suggests that learners are likely to succeed if instructional learning methodologies provide all pupils an equal opportunity, regardless of where they attend school. The conclusions of Amosun (2011), Borisade (2011), Obro (2016), Igwebuikwe and Ikpewonsa (2013), and others are in agreement with this. Other findings regarding the location of the school revealed that the mean test scores of urban and rural children differed significantly. These results were in line with earlier research that showed a large disparity between the mean scores of urban and rural children. According to their findings (Okonkwo et al., 2012), the location of the school has a considerable impact on kids' academic achievement. The results also shown how instructional learning styles improve students' academic achievement. The experimental and control groups' post-test mean scores demonstrated the impact of therapy. Additionally, the data's findings revealed that rural schools had better post-test mean scores than urban ones. In terms of statistics, the techniques used in this research could only reveal the variation in mean scores, not the extent of that variation.

Conclusion

It was concluded that there was effect of treatment on the experimental groups when compared with the control group. Those in the experimental groups showed that there was effect of treatment on school locations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and the conclusion reached, it was recommended as follows:

1. Interactive learning strategy and collaborative learning strategy should be used in the teaching and learning process of Social Studies. However, while doing this relative attention should be attached to sex and school location.
2. All students irrespective of sex and school location should be given the same level of encouragement and attention for better cognitive performance in Social Studies

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